

SEM PLS ANALYSIS OF WORK SPIRIT AND WORK ENVIRONMENT ON PERFORMANCE OF EDUCATIONAL ASN EMPLOYEES IN THE ENVIRONMENT OF THE STATE UNIVERSITY OF PADANG

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze and determine the effect of work enthusiasm and environment on ASN employees' performance. The academic staff at Padang State University (UNP). The population in this study amounted to 350 people and a sample of 78 people using the Slovin formula. The analytical method used is the Structural Equation Model Pls to see the relationship of each variable with its indicators or each variable's construct. The analysis results show that work enthusiasm has a positive and significant effect on the performance of ASN Education Personnel employees in the UNP environment. Likewise, the work environment has a positive and significant effect on the performance of ASN Education Personnel employees in the UNP environment. The contribution of work enthusiasm and work environment to the performance of ASN Education Personnel in UNP is 44.6%, and other variables outside of this study influence the remaining 55.4%.

Keywords: Morale, Work Environment, Performance, SEMPls.

A. INTRODUCTION

Academic staff is one of the important elements in the world of education. Although not the main element, education personnel play an important role in a university's sustainability. Realizing this, Padang State University made a guideline for evaluating the performance of education personnel to improve the quality of its academic staff. Academic staffs who have high quality and achievement will certainly improve university performance (Sa & Serpa, 2020).

Evaluation of the performance of education personnel is carried out to maintain the quality. With the performance evaluation, every education staff will have guidelines as a benchmark for their performance in the future. Every Education Personnel certainly needs feedback on their performance, which can guide their future performance. Therefore an assessment guideline that describes the performance of personnel is needed (Huber & Helm, 2020).

The performance assessment results can indicate whether the existing education personnel have met the standards desired by the university, both in terms of quality and quantity. The information in the Education Personnel performance assessment reflects the university's development (Regmi & Jones, 2020). Educational Personnel Performance Assessment is a systematic and structured approach used to measure, evaluate, and influence traits, behaviors, and results connected to the work place. Therefore, the performance evaluation is the consequence of personnel's work within the scope of their obligations (Shoaietal., 2022).

The performance of the Education Personnel at a higher education institution is a real behaviour displayed by each Education Personnel as the work performance produced by the Education Personnel following their role. To determine the quality of the performance of Education Personnel, it is necessary to have clear criteria (Gilal et al., 2019). Employee performance is an expression of the work performed by employees and is typically used as a basis or reference for evaluating personnel in an organization. Good performance contributes to the achievement of organizational objectives. Consequently, performance is also a factor in accomplishing organizational objectives, and efforts must be taken to enhance employee performance (Hendri, 2019).

The performance of education personnel is very important in the efforts of higher education institutions to achieve their goals. In a competitive and globalized world of competition, every university is required to be able to compete in meeting the demands of the world work market, for that it takes an important role from all parties, including the role of education staff (Al-Kurdi et al., 2018). At the same time, education personnel, as an important part of a university, need feedback from the institution on their work as a guide for their future performance. Through performance evaluation, the results of the performance assessment and feedback on the performance of the Education Personnel will be obtained. Performance appraisal of Education Personnel is a process in which the institution evaluates or assesses the performance of Education Personnel or evaluates the work of Education Personnel (Henderson et al., 2019).

Research conducted by previous researchers shows performance problems, where the performance of STIKes Harapan Bangsa Purwokerto employees is marked by the completion of work based on performance reports from each department in 2015, which is marked by 25 percent of lecturers and employees who do not carry outwork, while lecturers and employees who complete work but are late in completing work by 30 percent, based on the performance evaluation report by quality assurance Number: LPM.SHB.LK01 of 2015. Judging from these conditions indicates a performance problem. Therefore research is needed to analyze the causes of employee performance problems STIKes Harapan Bangsa Purwokerto (Pietrobon et al., 2020).

An employee is said to have high performance if the set work load is achieved and the realization of work results is higher than the target set by the organization. These demands that each employee cannot control will cause tension within employees so that employees will experience a decrease in performance (Han et al., 2020). To create good performance, employees strive to achieve goals to get maximum results in carrying out tasks in accordance with the responsibilities that have been given to achieve company goals. The decline in company performance will always be related to the performance of each employee itself (Davidescu et al., 2020).

Many factors can affect employee performance. Therefore it needs to be considered by the leadership so that employee performance can be optimal. There are both internal and external influences that affect a person's performance. Internal factors consist of attitudes, competencies, commitments, interests, discipline, organizational culture, morale, intellect, motivation, and personality (Jabeenet al., 2022). External determinants include facilities and

infrastructure, intensive or pay, commitment, work environment and atmosphere, organizational climate, and leadership style (Virgiawan et al., 2021).

The work environment is one of the elements that influence performance, because the work environment encompasses everything that can influence employees' ability to carry out their tasks and duties. A good work environment can support effective work implementation to create enthusiasm in work and improve employee performance (Diab-Bahman & Al-Enzi, 2020).

In addition to the work environment, another factor that affects performance is morale. Employee morale is a condition that arises from within a person, which causes a person to do his job in a happy atmosphere so that someone can work diligently, quickly, and be responsible for the company (Irawanto et al., 2021).

Padang State University (UNP) is one of the State Universities in Padang City, West Sumatra. Padang State University (UNP) aims to realize excellence in education through efforts to develop professional academic education. Therefore, to realize these advantages, of course, the role of employees is very important. Problems or obstacles that arise will cause losses that must be addressed immediately so that the goals of an organization are achieved (Bestari, 2020).

The results of initial observations conducted at the Padang State University (UNP) found problems regarding employee performance, where the quality and quantity of employee work is still low, there are still many employees who arrive late, the completion of the work of careless employees, causing student complaints and many other problems that arise occur. Based on the description above, the performance shows how employees work in carrying out their duties and the results achieved by employees from work (Adri & Abdullah, 2022).

Performance and morale are very important to be owned by employees because the spirit of the performance that is owned if done well, then the goals are achieved well. In other words, an employee's success is determined by the performance and morale shown in carrying out the duties and responsibilities they carry. In this study, two research variables were taken: the work environment and work spirit. Based on initial observations, it was found that these two variables had problems in the field (Bakti & Hartono, 2022).

Another phenomenon was observed and interviewed several Civil Servants (PNS) at the Padang State University about their work environment and work spirit. Some of the problems faced by these employees were (1) often arriving late; (2) always delegating work to co-workers; (3) using office facilities for personal purposes; (4) working slowly; and (5) adding longer rest periods (Sariwulan et al., 2019). Here the researchers took civil servants because most of them had problems with civil servants because, at any time, they could move to other parts of the work that were still within the scope of UNP (Veeramootoo et al., 2018). The condition of the work environment at the Padang State University Environment from a physical point of view has gone well where all facilities are well available, but from a non-physical perspective, there are many problems such as the lack of good relations between employees of different sections (Fonseca et al., 2021). Meanwhile, problems with morale can be seen that there are still problems with finishing work from finished work, the delivery of work results is

not on time, technical ability in completing work is low, mastery of extra and urgent tasks is still low, low cooperation in work, a low adjustment in job changes and low initiative in work (Riyanto et al., 2021). Another problem related to morale is shown in the following table:

Table 1: Data for UNP Civil Servants for January-December 2019 (Educational Personnel)

No.	Month	Working	Number of Employees	Overdue	Percentage
1	January	22	350	27	7,71
2	February	19	350	22	6,29
3	March	20	350	47	13,43
4	April	19	350	52	14,86
5	May	21	350	17	4,86
6	June	15	350	77	22,00
7	July	23	350	19	5,43
8	August	22	350	44	12,57
9	September	21	350	38	10,86
10	October	23	350	34	9,71
11	November	21	350	32	9,14
12	December	20	350	44	12,57

Based on table 1 above, it can be seen that the delay rate of civil servants at the Padang State University in 2019 in the January-December period. It can be seen that the highest delay occurred in June at 22% because, at that time, it coincided with Eid al-Fitr, and the lowest was in July. Meanwhile, the required absenteeism rate for PNS employees at Padang State University is 0.8% (Sub-Division of Educational Personnel for Padang State University Rectorate Employees 2019).

On the basis of the above, the problem can be stated as follows: Does the work atmosphere and morale of ASN Education Personnel staff at Padang State University effect their performance? (UNP).

B. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Performance

According to Mangkunegara, performance is derived from work performance or actual performance. Performance is the quality and amount of work accomplished by an employee in carrying out his obligations in accordance with his assigned duties. Performance is the outcome of a procedure measured over a specific time period in accordance with predetermined provisions or agreements (Hendri, 2019).

According to Mas'ud, performance indicators include work quality, work quantity, dependability, initiative, and craftsmanship. Robbins states that performance metrics include quality, quantity, timeliness, efficiency, independence, and job commitment (Abasimel, 2022). At the same time, the performance indicators according to Mangkunegara are the quality of work, quantity, implementation of duties, and responsibilities. Based on this, it can be concluded that the performance indicators that will be used in this research are (1) Quality of Work; (2) Quantity of Work; (3) Reliability; (4) Initiative; (5) Craft; (6) punctuality; and (7) responsibility (Sudiardithaet al., 2019). In conducting a performance appraisal, there must first be a standard of work. According to Sondang, Job Standards are several criteria that become a measure in performance appraisal, which is used as a comparison of the ways and results of carrying out the tasks of a job or position (Aras et al., 2018).

2. Work Environment

In addition to performance, the work environment is also a concern of an organization or institution so that its employees are enthusiastic about working. A work environment is a location where employees perform daily tasks. A secure and conducive work atmosphere enables individuals to perform their best work. The work environment can alter the emotions of employees (Rasool et al., 2021). If an employee enjoys his or her work environment, he or she will feel at ease at his or her office and engage in productive activities. According to Simanjuntak, the work environment generally consists of a physical and a psychological work environment (Newman & Ford, 2021).

According to Sedarmayanti, the indicators of the work environment include illumination, air temperature at work, security, air circulation, and workplace decoration. According to Saydam, the work environment indicators are physical and non-physical (Baharuddin, 2021). Meanwhile, Nitisemito describes that the work environment indicators consist of a work atmosphere, relationships with colleagues, and the availability of work facilities. The work environment indicators used in this study are physical and physical (Geiger & Pivovarova, 2018). A good and conducive work environment will encourage employees' work spirit in their work so that they can improve their performance. The definition of morale, according to Nitisemito, is something positive and something good so that it can contribute to its work in a better sense. According to Sondang, morale is the extent to which employees are passionate about carrying out their duties and responsibilities within the company (Yunus et al., 2020).

The factors that influence the decline and weakening of morale are low wages, poor work environment, lack of discipline, poor leadership style, and lack of information. Therefore, the company must strive to maintain employee morale by doing various ways and combinations of which are achieved such as adequate salary, paying attention to spiritual needs, the need to create a relaxed atmosphere, placing employees in the right position, feeling safe and the future and facilities that are good (Hasan et al., 2018). The indicators of morale that the researcher uses in this study are (1) Employee Productivity; (2) Absenteeism Level; (3) Labor Turn Over; and (4) discipline.

C. METHOD

This study was conducted at Padang State University by sending questionnaires to the university's education faculty. This study's population consisted of 350 individuals from 16 work units at UNP. The Slovin formula was used to obtain a sample of 78 individuals. The sampling was conducted using a proportional random sampling technique that offered each element (member) of the population with equal chances of being picked as a sample member.

The analytical method used in this research is a descriptive analysis of variables and quantitative analysis. The descriptive analysis explains the results of respondents' answers in filling out the questionnaire given for each indicator of the variables studied. Quantitative analysis is used to see the effect of exogenous variables (work spirit and work environment) on endogenous variables (Performance) using path analysis. The data analysis technique used SEM through the SmartPLS 3.0 program. Hypothesis testing is done by t-test (partial) with an error tolerance of 5%. Before further analysis, the research instrument was tested (questionnaire with validity and reliability tests).

D. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Results of Variable Descriptive Analysis

a) Spirit at work

The employee productivity indicator shows that, on average, the respondents answered with the statement Always (SL) as many as 31 people (40.17). This means that employees have high work productivity and can do their jobs wherever they are placed. Even employees can do their jobs well even though it is beyond their skills. However, some respondents still answer with rare and occasional statements, which show that most employees cannot do their jobs well if placed in places that are not following their skills. This, of course, will impact the productivity of the work that will be produced. For the Attendance indicator, the average number of employees answered with statements sometimes with a percentage of 41% (32 people). This proves that employees still do not realize the importance of absenteeism or attendance in carrying out their duties and coming on time. Some employees even leave their work during office hours without asking for permission.

The labor turnover indicator shows that, on average, the respondents answered with statements sometimes by 38% (30 people). This means that there is still a desire from employees to move or leave their jobs, and there is also a desire from these employees to seek information about new jobs. As for the indicators of discipline, the average respondent also answered with statements sometimes as many as 32 people (41%) where it can be seen that the level of employee discipline is still low because there are still some employees who think that they come on time and complete tasks following the time is not an important thing to pay attention to. Overall, it can be concluded from the results of the respondents' answers that the morale of the employees at the Padang State University is still relatively low because the average respondent's answers to all the statements submitted in the questionnaire are often answered with options sometimes and rarely. Low morale will certainly have an impact on the

performance produced by employees. Therefore, there is a need for a renewal and better motivation to increase employees' morale in the UNP environment.

b) Work environment

The average number of respondents answered with good statements (always and often) as many as 40 people (52%). This indicates that physically the work environment at Padang State University is adequate where the employee's workspace is equipped with CCTV, has ventilation for the entry and exit of air circulation, and there is also security that maintains the safety of the employees who work.

For non-physical environmental indicators, on average, many respondents answered with negative statements (sometimes and rarely), with a total of 44 respondents (56%). This means that the non-physical work environment, which includes the relationship between fellow subordinates, and the relationship between subordinates and superiors, has not been going well. This can be seen from respondents stating that there is still competition among fellow employees, and sometimes the leadership acts unfairly toward all employees. This condition will certainly impact the performance of employees at Padang State University.

c) Performance

The indicators of the quantity of work, the average respondent answered with statements sometimes as much as 44% (34 people). This means that in terms of quantity of work, employees in the UNP environment do not have too many jobs, and there are even jobs that are not following their knowledge or skills. For indicators of work quality, there are still many respondents who have not completed their work properly. This can be seen from the results of the respondents' answers with the most statements, namely sometimes, which means that many of their work completions are not following the standards that have been set.

For reliability indicators, it shows that employees are reliable enough in doing the work assigned to them, where respondents answered with statements sometimes as much as 44%. This also explains that employees can still do their jobs even though they are placed anywhere by the leadership. However, guidance and training are still needed to maximize the work's completion. For indicators of initiative, craftsmanship, punctuality, and responsibility, the average respondent answered with statements sometimes. This explains that there are still many ASN employees. Academic staff in the UNP environment do not have a high initiative in completing work, there are still those who don't come on time, and there are even those who do not have a high commitment and responsibility to complete their work on time.

2. Quantitative Analysis Results

a) Outer Model

The outer model aims to see whether each indicator relates to its latent variable. Analysis of the data in this study using software smartPLS 3.0. The outer model test consists of 3 stages: convergent validity, discriminant validity, and composite reliability. The results of the three tests can be explained as follows:

1. Convergent Validity Test

The convergent validity test is seen from the loading factor value of the indicators that measure these variables. According to Hair, exploratory factor analysis is an approach to investigating the factors contained in the observed variables. Therefore, the loading factor criteria for exploratory research must be greater than 0.7 (≥ 0.7). The results of the convergent validity analysis with smart PIs are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Convergent Validity Test Results

Based on Figure 2, it can be seen that the loading factor value of each indicator, where several indicators have a coefficient value of <0.7 , namely the PD3, LT3, DS1, FS1, FS5, NF1, NF3, NF4, NF5, Qn1, Qn3 indicators, QL1, QI3, HD3, and IS3. Therefore, all indicators with an LF value below 0.7 will be deleted for further analysis.

The results of the second analysis can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Output Path Coefficient Fit

Figure 3 above shows that the LF values of all indicators are already above 0.7, so this shows an appropriate relationship between the latent variable and the indicator. The results of the outer loading output can be seen in table 2.

Table 2: Output Outer Loading

Variable	Indicator	Code Indicator	Load Factor Value
Morale (X1)	Employee Productivity	PD1	0.957
	Attendance	PD2	0.964
		AB1	0.785
		AB2	0.811
		AB3	0.793
		Labour Turn Over	LT1
	LT2		0.912
	Discipline	DS2	0.786
		DS3	0.877
	Work Environment (X2)	Physical Environment	FS2
FS3			0.898
FS4			0.879
Non-Physical Environment		NF2	1,000
Performance (Y)	Working Quantity	Qn1	1,000
	Work quality	QL2	1,000
	Reliability	HD1	0.891
		HD2	0.917
	Initiative	IS1	0.900
		IS2	0.907
	Craft	RJ1	0.748
		RJ2	0.765
		RJ3	0.773
	On-time	OT1	0.854
		OT2	0.934
		OT3	0.918
	Responsibility	RS1	0.792
		RS2	0.810
		RS3	0.751

On the basis of table 2, where each indicator's LF value is greater than 0.7, it may be inferred that all indicators of endogenous construct variables are legitimate.

2. Discriminant Validity Test

The discriminant validity test compares the values in the cross-loading table to determine the reflected indicators of each variable. A valid indication has the highest loading factor value for the intended construct relative to other constructions.

Table 3: Output Cross Loading

Indicator	Morale (X1)	Work Environment (X2)	Performance (Y)
PD1	0.957	0.099	-0.076
PD2	0.964	0.120	-0.041
AB1	0.785	0.295	0.399
AB2	0.811	0.063	0.545
AB3	0.793	0.020	0.419
LT1	0.931	0.238	0.438
LT2	0.912	0.259	0.420
DS2	0.786	0.241	0.408
DS3	0.877	0.183	0.406
FS2	0.154	0.870	0.218
FS3	0.060	0.898	0.296
FS4	0.154	0.879	0.337
NF2	0.352	1,000	0.334
Qn1	0.437	0.194	1,000
QL2	0.005	0.253	1,000
HD1	0.308	0.447	0.891
HD2	0.389	0.518	0.917
IS1	0.082	0.286	0.900
IS2	0.190	0.043	0.907
RJ1	0.409	0.196	0.748
RJ2	0.696	0.296	0.765
RJ3	0.585	0.145	0.773
OT1	0.229	0.269	0.854
OT2	0.302	0.287	0.934
OT3	0.181	0.209	0.918
RS1	0.385	0.162	0.792
RS2	0.521	0.162	0.810
RS3	0.638	-0.046	0.751

3. Composite Reliability Test

A latent variable can be said to have good reliability if the Composite Reliability value is greater than 0.7 and Cronbach's alpha value is greater than 0.7. The results of the reliability test are as follows.

Table 4: Latent Variable Reliability Test Results

Construct Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Information
Morale (X1)	0.829	0.863	Reliable
Work Environment (X2)	0.759	0.816	Reliable
Performance (Y)	0.832	0.856	Reliable

Table 4 shows that all latent variables measured in this study have Cronbach's Alpha and composite reliability values > 0.7, so it can be concluded that all latent variables are reliable.

b) Evaluation of the Structural Model (Inner Model)

The inner model is evaluated using R square (coefficient of determination) for the independent variables. To test the hypothesis using a t-test and significance.

1. Test R Square

The results of the R square test can be seen in table 5.

Table 5: Results of R square

Variable	R-square
Performance (Y)	0.446

The value of R Square in table 5 is 0.446, which means that the contribution of the variable morale and work environment to performance is 44.6%, while the remaining 55.4% is influenced by other constructs that are not used in this research model.

2. Significance Test

The significance test aims to test the hypothesis and the effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables. Hypothesis testing was carried out through the bootstrapping process using the smartPls 3.0 program with a significance level of 0.05. The results of the path coefficient and t-statistics can be seen in table 6.

Table 6: Path Analysis Results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Performance -> Initiative	0.468	0.457	0.145	3,224	0.001
Performance ->Reliability	0.752	0.750	0.058	12,899	0.000
Performance ->Craft	0.715	0.718	0.077	9,319	0.000
Performance ->Quality_Work	0.211	0.211	0.163	1,299	0.194
Performance ->Quantity_Work	0.544	0.543	0.095	5,705	0.000
Performance ->_Responsibility	0.843	0.840	0.046	18,235	0.000
Performance -> On Time	0.812	0.809	0.058	14,099	0.000
Work_Environment ->Physical	0.900	0.900	0.027	33,483	0.000
Work_Environment -> Performance	0.239	0.252	0.114	2,105	0.036
Work_Environment ->Non Physical	0.645	0.638	0.102	6,319	0.000
Spirit_Work -> Attendance	0.871	0.863	0.039	22,424	0.000
Passion_Work -> Discipline	0.857	0.858	0.029	29,729	0.000
Passion_Work -> Performance	0.560	0.548	0.117	4,786	0.000
Passion_Work ->Labor_Turn Over	0.810	0.809	0.038	21,562	0.000
Passion_Work ->Productivity_Work	0.185	0.181	0.189	0.976	0.330

Based on table 6, it can be interpreted as follows:

- The path coefficient value of the work environment on performance is positive at 0.239 and a significance value of $0.036 < 0.05$. This means that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. So it can be concluded that the work environment significantly positively affects the performance of employees at Padang State University.
- The Path Coefficient of Morale on performance is positive at 0.560 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, which means that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. So it can be concluded that work spirit has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Padang State University.

3. The Influence of Work Morale on Performance

With a path coefficient of 0.56, the findings of the path analysis and hypothesis t-test indicate that workplace morale has a positive and statistically significant effect on employee performance. This means that if employee morale increases, employee performance will also increase. Employee morale is a condition that arises from within a person, which causes a person to do his job in a happy atmosphere so that someone can work diligently and quickly and be responsible for the company.

Morale, according to Nitisemito is something positive and good so that it can contribute to its work in a better sense. According to Sondang, morale is the extent to which employees are passionate about carrying out their duties and responsibilities within the company (Ramos-Morcillo et al., 2020). Thus, morale can move people to work and complete their work better. Therefore, the organization or company must always strive to motivate employees to have high morale. This, of course, will have an impact on improving its performance.

This research is also supported by previous research conducted by Anggreni, where his research shows that work spirit has a significant positive effect on performance. Likewise, with research by Cahya, the study results found an effect of morale on performance. In another study by Pasaribu, the results found that there was an influence of work spirit on performance (Lopez & Tucker, 2019).

4. Influence of Work Environment on Performance

The path analysis and hypothesis t-test indicate that the work environment has a significant positive effect on the performance of civil servants (PNS) at the Padang State University (UNP). The better the work environment of an institution, the higher the performance of its employees.

The work environment is one of the elements that influence performance, because the work environment encompasses everything that can influence employees' ability to carry out their tasks and duties. A good work environment can support effective work implementation to create enthusiasm in work and improve employee performance.

Gitahi Njenga Samson's research revealed that psychosocial factors had the largest correlation with employee performance, while physical and psychological factors had a minor relationship. It is suggested that consideration be made to the physical and work-life balance components of

employment environments (Alkhamees et al., 2020). This indicates that the psychosocial factor has the largest correlation with employee performance, whilst the physical and psychological aspects have a moderate link. It is suggested that consideration be given to various affects of the work-life environment, such as physical balance and work-life factors. According to the findings of Adytia's research, all variables have a substantial impact on employee performance concurrently.

This research is backed by Wijaya and Susanty's research. The data indicate that the work environment affects employee performance. Another study by Syardiansah and Utami revealed that the work environment had an effect on employee performance. Hendry's research demonstrates a correlation between the Work Environment and Employee Performance (Eliyana&Ma'arif, 2019).

Also, research conducted by Darmalisstates that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Regional Development Planning Agency (Bappeda) of West Sumatra Province, and research by Hariyono et al. states that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on the Performance of Public Relations and Protocol Officers of the Regional Secretariat of Ponorogo Regency (Kurnia et al., 2022). This study, however, contradicts the findings of Logahan et al. and Kusumayanti et al., who concluded that the work environment has no effect on employee performance (Tran et al., 2018).

5. The Influence of Work Spirit and Work Environment on Performance

The coefficient of determination, or R square, has a value of 0.446%. This indicates that work morale and work environment contribute 44.6 percent to performance. Together with the work environment and work spirit, these characteristics have a substantial impact on the performance of government servants (PNS) education staff at Padang State University (UNP). Performance and morale are very important to be owned by employees because the spirit of the performance that is owned if done well, then the goals are achieved well. In other words, an employee's success is determined by the performance and morale shown in carrying out the duties and responsibilities they carry.

A person's performance (individual) is closely related to the productivity of the organization/company (Corporate Performance). In other words, the good performance of employees will considerably impact the company's productivity. When he feels the need to work, whether it comes from himself or the organization, a skilled employee will strive to perform at his best (Rumanti et al., 2022). Internal motivations to work, such as the abilities acquired by the employee, follow the work being performed. The effect of the company's encouragement in the form of a high salary, a comfortable environment, and awards given to the employee so that a group of employees has good performance can be seen in the company's productivity, namely the achievement of company goals in accordance with their vision and mission (Chien et al., 2020).

E. CONCLUSION

This study concludes, based on the preceding discussion, that work excitement has a positive and statistically significant effect on the performance of ASN Education Personnel at Padang State University, with a significance level of $0.036 < 0.05$. Consequently, the work environment has a favorable and substantial influence on the performance of ASN Education Personnel at Padang State University, with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$. The contribution of work excitement and work environment to the performance of ASN Education Personnel at Padang State University is 44,6 percent, while the remaining 55,4 percent is influenced by other variables not considered in this study, such as motivational leadership, work stress, etc.

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